

Analysis of the Classical Management Approach, a Descriptive View

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ABSTRACT

An approach to the management approach is made, starting from the classical or traditional theory of Henry Fayol. Theory that establishes the functions and principles of management applied to organizations. Analyze the approaches to management, starting from the classical theory also known as "traditional", where Henry Fayol established the functions and principles of management that should be carried out within any organization.

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INTRODUCTION

Analysis of the classical administration approach, a descriptive look, presents a critical approach to its development throughout history, also considering the contribution of the different representatives, and especially its main exponent Henry Fayol. The classical theory of administration, born in France in 1916 in which Henry Fayol exposes his theory in his famous book *Industrial and General Administration* published in Paris in 1916. (Ruiza, 2004). According to the above, the mining engineer gives life to the classical theory with the publication of his book, becoming one of the most representative authors of the classical thought of the Administration.

Fayol, in the classical theory of administration, or as it is also called traditional administration, defends an administration model that is based on three fundamental aspects: the division of labor, the application of the administrative process and the formulation of technical criteria that should guide the administrative function. (Martinez, 2016) in such a way that by taking these three aspects into account, the administration of any organization will be better oriented towards the achievement of its organizational objectives and therefore the results of organizational management will be focused on making the organization a more competitive economic entity. The classical studies of administration theory have supported a concept of rational organization (Taylor, Fayol) according to which individuals were considered mere vehicles of said rationality. (Perlo, n.d.)

The classical administration approach, at present, also has applicability in many organizations, since it meets the expectations that organizations require at the managerial level and establishes general principles that must be followed according to the activity of the company. Regarding the principles, these were developed by Fayol and which will be discussed later.

The classical theory of administration is formulated at the beginning of the 20th century. (Omar, 1999). Taylor, the father of management, as he is known; analyzes jobs and manufacturing operations, seeking to improve efficiency and labor productivity. Process that allows to know the times and movements required for each task, the human skills required for each task, which allows to establish salaries based on production.

Fayol, for his part, carries out an extension of this process to the entire organization, Taylor's factory analysis, formulating principles for management and identifying the basic areas of the organization. Although these principles are criticized and qualified as proverbs by Simon (1947), they serve as the basis for programming, coordination, management by objectives and the development of business consulting (Perrow, 1991) cited by (Omar, 1999).

The excessive rigidity and linearity of the model and the omission of the human aspects of the organization greatly affect the validity of this theory, although the ideas of Taylor and Fayol maintain their influence intact in various aspects. (Omar, 1999) and differ in approach, Fayol and Taylor believe that management must go beyond the fully empirical level to become a science. (Espinoza Sotomayor Roberto, 2009) Regarding science, it can be analyzed that it is a system of components that emphasize the structure of the organization. For

Fayol, the administration is a whole and a set of processes of which the organization is one of the parts, and this in turn is static and limited, since it refers to the structure and form.(López D. María Esperanza et al., 2006) With the classical administration approach, it was possible to determine a set of operations that are carried out daily in companies, which are divided into six groups: technical operations, refers to those activities that are carried out in the company by production, manufacturing or transformation. , which are related to the same area, generating the product or service that is finally offered to the customer.

It should be noted that all the operations, number, quantity or of any nature, generally come from the technicians, this is an important function but not the only one that the organization can have in place since the six work together.(Jenny Martinez Jenny Martinez Crespo, 2005)

As for the commercial functions, they are the activities carried out by a team of professionals in the organization, they are dedicated to buying and selling the products and services that it markets. This area or function of the company is the one that interacts or is the link between the company and customers, since they are the ones who offer, advise and sell the product to the final consumer. The strength of this function is the ability, skill and commercial astuteness of the seller when offering the product or service, in addition to the deep knowledge of the market and the strength of its competitors.

A third group is made up of financial functions, without a doubt it is one of the most important parts within an organization, since financial management and cash flow in the company are the main focus for decision-making in administrations and a good planning in it.

Financial capital is necessary to cover the expenses incurred by the entity, whether operational or administrative, as well as for the acquisition of goods, tools and raw materials. If the company does not have economic solvency, it is impossible for it to achieve a prosperous life, no reform, no improvement is achieved without availability or credit.

Security functions have as objective the care of goods and people against accidents and the protection of all the processes and resources of the information systems, in addition it seeks the well-being of the employees and of those who are directly or indirectly linked to it, adopts new security strategies within the organization.

Accounting functions, it is the body that serves the company to make decisions, since at any time it allows its managers to know where they are and where they are going, the information must be understandable, useful, pertinent, timely, reliable and comparable. When accounting is simple and clear, it gives an idea of the conditions in which the company is. Administrative functions, in charge of coordinating the other five functions. Since it is the area that plans, organizes, directs, coordinates and controls.

It can be evidenced, after this description of the functions that are key to the classical theory, the way in which Fayol raises the administration as an activity common to all organizations, be it in an industrial company, the government or the army. Fayol believed that a general knowledge of administration would benefit all countries and should therefore be taught in schools and universities. In addition, he stressed that all organizations require a certain degree of planning, organization, direction, coordination, and control. What for him became what is known as the classical theory of administration.

Authors such as Koontz and Weihrich (1999), and Robbins and Coulter (2000), express that, in the current competitive context, administration is one of the most important human activities. Every organization requires making decisions, coordinating multiple activities, managing people, evaluating performance, getting and allocating different resources, and more.

It is observed, then, that the administration must fulfill a series of responsibilities that will require, in a changing environment, greater knowledge and adopt new positions and approaches, according to the various situations. In short, Fayol manages to turn a company in crisis into a productive and competitive company. Determining that the administrative process in light of the classical theory of administration is composed of proper planning, direction, organization, coordination and control (Fayol, 2009).

Through these processes, the manager of the organizations plans the activities, previously and with the available resources, organizes the elements that are fundamental for the administration, determines the procedures to guide and orient the personnel involved in the action, developing tasks of coordination and control, so that the administration of the organization has a common thread that generates productivity and stability. In this way, he divided administrative operations into groups of related activities, describing the main functions that should be performed in any organization. It is based on the importance of the formal structure of organizations, such as science, administration, must be supported by laws or flexible principles that adapt to different circumstances of time or place. (Martinez Fajardo, 1999)

Being a manager in today's organization implies taking on the role of agent of change and transformation of the organization, leading it in new directions, new processes and new technologies. Therefore, new and updated administrative practices are required in order to be able to face aspects such as globalization, technology and complex social changes, among others, which represent a significant challenge for contemporary organizations. However, the classic concept of administration continues to be decisive, since it sees the process of organizations as an integrated whole, a system of elements that must be intertwined, coordinated and controlled under the magnifying glass of a common objective.

In accordance with the above, the Classical Theory sees the organization as a closed system, disregarding environmental influences and making unrealistic assumptions about human behavior, its principles and foundations being contradictory.(Medina Macías & Vidal, 2002) The classical school approach to the field of administration is concerned with specifying the quantity of subordinates for an effective scope. Traditional management theorists take the position that there are too many variables underlying a management situation for it to be possible. specify a specific number of subordinates that a manager can supervise effectively.(Koontz et al., 2012)

Cejas and Jácome (2006) point out that current organizations need to get in tune with the rapid changes that are occurring today in humanity. Certainly, as a consequence of social development, new realities and new forms are emerging. And to achieve this, you cannot ignore the classical theory of administration, which He considers that the aspects of this theory are developed in the division of tasks, application of authority and assignment of responsibility.(Medina Macías & Vidal, 2002)

Now, given the importance of the classical theory of administration, which has been described throughout this argument, it is important to dwell on the principles that are fundamental for the application of the administrative process according to the classical theory, which are defined by Fayol as:the division of labor, authority, discipline, unity of command, unity of direction, subordination of the individual good to the common good, remuneration of the personnel, centralization, hierarchy, order, equity, stability of the personnel, initiative and team spirit.(Medina Macías & Vidal, 2002)

Once in the concept of classical theory, its aspects, elements, process in general, it is also important to recognize some contradictions of this theory that become relevant at the time of its application, suddenly becoming obstacles to organizational evolution. The classical theory cThe organization is conceived under rigid and formal terms, without taking into account the importance of its social aspect, It is based on observation and common sense, the absence of experimental work is evident, which is a requirement of industrial and technological development today, the extreme use of rationalism is evident, sometimes sacrificing the clarity of its ideas. Finally, according to modern administrators, it is called the theory of the machine, which establishes that given certain actions, certain consequences will occur. A precedent is set in the achievement of proposed goals in an effective way, so the application of its methods, techniques and principles has been observed in many companies even today to achieve their objectives and economic purpose.(Omar, 1999)

LITERATURE REVIEW

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METHODOLOGY

Now, having already described in its fundamental aspects the classical theory of administration, it is pertinent that we stop to review it in a practical way. The company that was chosen is a very large international company, this company is The Coca-Cola Company, according to what has been investigated, this company implements many of the principles given in the classical theory of administration, such as .

1. The division of labor, since each worker in the company specializes in a specific field, it is also noted that each job post has a manual of functions and this in turn can be subordinated to other positions, taking into account that it is They can delegate functions, but not responsibilities.
2. Unity of direction, the company stands out because it has a single vision in all its factories, which is: Guide every aspect of our company, describing what we need to achieve in order to continue producing sustainable and quality growth. In other words, it is about establishing a coordinated process where everyone looks in the same direction, seeking to achieve the Mission and Vision that the organization has conceived.
3. Teamwork, since the bosses seek to motivate the worker, to do teamwork, thus reaching greater productivity. This aspect is considered fundamental because the company or organization is conceived as a productive unit and its main resource is human capital.
4. Hierarchy, the company has a hierarchical command pyramid, where the general manager is the one with the highest rank.
5. Of authority and responsibility, this has to do with the previous principle, since, in companies, the higher the hierarchy you have, the greater your authority and responsibility will be.

In itself, the company is linked to this theory of administration, but not completely, as is common with every company, it takes the best of each theory and applies it to itself, thus giving a better organization and better profitability for the company.

As can be seen and in accordance with the above, Organizations have been changing over the years, more so with the arrival of the industrial revolution and with the new discoveries of science, which have generated changes in the way organizations operate and in their way of satisfying customers. clients, who in

turn have changed over the years and whose needs have radically changed (Alvarado, Romero & Otro, 2007). This constitutes a challenge for current organizations, since the new type of human being is more demanding.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

According to Celaya (2015), organizations have very different needs than they had before as a result of factors such as globalization and new technological advances.

The administrative operation of Coca Cola is based on the classical theory of administration, which conceives of the organization as a structure and seeks the efficiency of the organization based on 4 stages: planning, organization, control and direction. This will later be considered neoclassical theory. In Coca Cola, there is a division of labor and then there is an authority that guides the other workers so that activities are carried out in the most efficient and effective way and this is a main characteristic of the classical theory of Administration. Within the classical theory of administration, Coca Cola stands out for being one of the world's leading companies and Fayol's 14 principles could easily be identified in it.

It is important to clarify that even under the principles of classical management theory, Coca Cola is currently a recognized and positioned brand worldwide, being sold in more than 205 countries. Maintaining the volume of its sales thanks to its continuous marketing and advertising campaigns, which are characterized by being multicultural innovators. The objective is to stay in the minds of consumers and win the acceptance and preference of the new generations. Coca Cola has an organizational structure by division, since Coca Cola, in addition to producing and distributing the most popular international brands, also has drinks that adapt to the tastes of each region. It has some flavors that are more popular in certain countries, plus there are different ingredients that distinguish them from the rest.

- Leadership: striving to shape a better future.
- Collaboration: promoting collective talent.
- Integrity: be transparent.
- Accountability: be responsible.
- Passion: be committed with the heart and mind.
- Diversity: have a wide range of brands and be as inclusive as them.
- Quality: pursuit of excellence.

When we stop at the analysis of each of the values of the COCA COLA company, there is a special relationship with each of the principles of administration in relation to the division of labor, management, quality, teamwork.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

As a conclusion, it is noted, after this bibliographic search that Companies tend to apply some or a combination of administrative theories or approaches with their characteristics and their conceptualization defined according to their time and the context of their country. Although it is true there is no formula to achieve success in the administration of a company; In the present work, the philosophy of those Mexican companies that have managed to excel in modern times is analyzed.

At the beginning, the Mexican companies that are successful in the Mexican market are mentioned. It is worth mentioning that several of them have internationalized.

Regarding the organizations and their administrative principles, the texts embodied in the types of planning such as principles, rules, values, among others, are reviewed, by making a comparison between the conceptualization of each of the theories and the philosophy of the companies are identified. characteristics established in the classical theory of administration emphatically. Therefore, it is important to recognize the tendency that still exists today towards classical administration theories and whose administration has allowed them to achieve the success they have in the current time and context.

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